

An Overview of Patented Cultivars in *Aloë*, *Aristaloë*, ×*Aristeria*, *Astroloba*, ×*Gasteraloë*, *Gasteria*, *Gonialoë*, *Haworthiopsis*, and *Tulista* (Aloaceae)

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The following patented cultivars in the Aloaceae family are listed in the Google Patents Search engine, which indexes more than 87 million patents and patent applications, including plant patents. A newly developed or discovered asexually produced cultivar can be patented to give its so-called ‘inventor’ the ‘right to exclude others from asexually reproducing the plant, and from using, offering for sale, or selling the plant so reproduced, or any of its parts’ for a period of 20 years (United States Patent and Trademark Office 2019).

For every cultivar the cultivar name, the correct genus, the genus under which it was patented, the parentage, the name of the inventor, the patent number and date, and the distinguishing features are listed. The distinguishing features sections were copied from the patent files and only slightly edited for brevity; they were not critically evaluated. For every cultivar an illustration is included. Unfortunately all illustrations in Google Patents are scans of poor-quality printouts that seem to have been faxed.

Aloë 'Aloejaws'

Aloë melanacantha

INVENTOR/PATENT

Johannes H. A. Ammerlaan
US20160183439P1, 18 Dec 2014

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Dark green foliage; upright growth habit; short leaves and a compact size; an abundance of white foliar spines.

***Aloë* 'ANDora'**

Aloë hybrid × *Aloë* hybrid

INVENTOR/PATENT

Charles A. de Wet
USPP28003P3, 19 Feb 2015

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Light orange-colored flowers; light greyish-green colored foliage; moderately vigorous growth rate; upright-compact growth habit.

***Aloë* 'Blizzard'**

Aloë 'Doran Black' × *Aloë* hybrid

INVENTOR/PATENT

Renee O'Connell
USPP21408P2, 6 Jun 2009

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Upright plant morphology; bright white foliage variegation; frequent blooming periods; small plant size; free offset production.

Aloë 'DEMI'

Aloë rauhii

INVENTOR/PATENT

Johannes H. A. Ammerlaan
USPP29485P3, 17 May 2017

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Flattened globular profile with foliage arranged in a short, compact rosette; strong foliage with a broad ovate to near deltoid shape and a long apiculate apex; dark green foliage; foliage that is densely covered with raised elongated papillae, white in general coloration, on both the adaxial and abaxial surfaces; an abundance of papillae which are tightly arranged longitudinal rows across the entire adaxial and abaxial leaf surfaces.

Aloë 'Ovaljaws'

Aloë melanacantha

INVENTOR/PATENT

Johannes H. A. Ammerlaan
USPP28328P3, 18 Dec 2014

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

dark green foliage; upright growth habit; short leaves and a compact size; an abundance of white foliar spines.

***Aloë* ‘Pickled Pink’**

(Aloë rauhii × *Aloë parvula)* ×
(Aloë parvula × *Aloë capitata)*

INVENTOR/PATENT

Renee O’Connell

USPP22227P2, 6 Jun 2009

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Very papillose texture to leaves; jewel-like appearance to leaves with bright coral leaf margins and papillae, overlaid with glaucous blue green patina; very floriferous; upright morphology; unusual coral margins and papillae almost appear fluorescent at certain angles.

***Aloë* ‘Saenjang’**

Aloë vera?

INVENTOR/PATENT

Kwon Hee Kim

WO2016171344A1, 23 Apr 2015

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

‘[G]rows to a height of 30 ~ 55cm of the body, the stem is long and soft leaves grown to give way, almost no growth after 1-2 year growth, the growth of leaves length 40cm, has white spots on a pale green background and about the width of 6cm, the yen has a small and weak visible edges of the leaves. Further growth of aloe growing near the roots of young seedlings ipmom least 5-20, and the thickness of the shell is thinner than vera leaves may have a characteristic spine does not hurt a thing.’

***Aloë* 'Safari Rose'**

Aloë hybrid × *Aloë* hybrid

INVENTOR/PATENT

Charles A. de Wet

US20160249511P1, 19 Feb 2015

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Light salmon-pink colored flowers; medium green-colored foliage tipped with greyed-red; moderately vigorous growth rate; upright-compact growth habit.

***Aloë* 'X5'**

Aloë hybrid × *Aloë* hybrid

INVENTOR/PATENT

Charles A. de Wet, Quinton Been

USPP23267P2, 25 Mar 2011

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Vigorous growth rate; short and compact plant habit; abundance of inflorescences on strong erect scapes; flowers that are greenish white in color and emerge from red-orange flower buds forming a bicolored inflorescence.

***Aristaloë* ‘AMIAL1605’**

(*Aloë* ‘AMIAL1605’)

Aristaloë aristata

INVENTOR/PATENT

Gerard van Langen

USPP28982P2, 11 Aug 2016

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Thick succulent foliage, arranged in a basal rosette, with a flattened globular profile and a shorter overall plant height; foliage that is slightly curved upward, with innermost whorls of foliage appearing to be more loosely held; ovate foliage with dentate leaf margins, an acute to broadly acute apex, and a short caudate tip; dark green mature foliage with a moderately dense occurrence of prominent white papillae on both the adaxial and abaxial surfaces.

***Aristaloë* ‘AMIAL1614’**

(*Aloë* ‘AMIAL1614’)

Aristaloë aristata

INVENTOR/PATENT

Gerard van Langen

USPP28948P2, 30 Jan 2017

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Erect foliage arranged in a basal rosette; ark green foliage which is densely covered with large, prominent papillae on both the adaxial and abaxial surfaces, and large prominent spines along the margins; large papillae which are colored white, and occasionally bearing spines; papillae on the abaxial leaf surface which are arranged in distinct transverse rows.

***Aristaloë* ‘AMIAL1619’**

(*Aloë* ‘AMIAL1619’)

Aloë aristata

INVENTOR/PATENT

Gerard van Langen

USPP28947P2, 3 Feb 2017

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Erect to slightly inward-facing foliage arranged in a spreading basal rosette, with foliage in the innermost whorls held very tightly; large deltoid leaves with a soft mucronulate apex; dark green foliage that is densely covered with prominent papillae on both the adaxial and abaxial surfaces; papillae near the margins and apex which bear spines; papillae on the abaxial leaf surface which are arranged in distinct transverse rows, and bearing spines in a distinct longitudinal row along the midrib.

***Aristaloë* ‘AMIAL1620’**

(*Aloë* ‘AMIAL1620’)

Aristaloë aristata

INVENTOR/PATENT

Gerard van Langen

USPP29024P2 3 Feb 2017

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Flattened globular profile with foliage arranged in a short, compact rosette; short, broad foliage; foliage that is dark green where exposed to ultraviolet light and yellow green where not directly exposed to

light; foliage that is densely covered with prominent papillae on both the adaxial and abaxial surfaces; papillae on the abaxial leaf surface which are arranged in distinct transverse rows, and bearing spines in a distinct longitudinal row along the midrib.

×*Aristeria* ‘AMIAL1622’

(*Gasteria* AMIAL1622)

Aristaloë aristata × *Gasteria carinata*

INVENTOR/PATENT

Gerard van Langen

USPP29138P2, 3 Feb 2017

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Thick succulent foliage with an erect to arched attitude, arranged in a compact rosette; large leaves that are near ovate to deltoid in shape, with an apiculate apex; dark green leaves which are moderately covered with white papillae on the adaxial leaf surface and densely covered with near white papillae on the abaxial leaf surface.

×*Aristeria* 'Aurora'

(×*Gasteraloë* 'Aurora')
Gasteria 'Royal Wolfgang' ×
Aristaloë aristata

INVENTOR/PATENT

Obed J. Smit
USPP29283P3, 26 Sep 2016

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Green leaves with white spots;
leaf margins with white teeth;
basal rosette plant shape.

×*Aristeria* 'D Sigma'

(×*Gasteraloë* 'D Sigma')
×*Aristeria beguinii* nothovar.
perfectior

INVENTOR/PATENT

Christian Jachertz
USPP29486P3, 5 Dec 2016

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Green leaves with large white
dots; leaf margins with white
teeth; flattened rosette plant
shape.

***Astroloba* 'OVASDINO'**

Astroloba spiralis

INVENTOR/PATENT

Johannes H. A. Ammerlaan
US20170257995P1, 3 Mar 2016

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Large plant size with foliage arranged in a single non-branched basal rosette, forming a short stem with time; large, dark green leaves which are lightly covered with light green papillae on the adaxial leaf surface and moderately to heavily covered with light green papillae on the abaxial leaf surface; dentate leaf margins with relatively large spines.

×*Gasteraloë* 'Tiki Zilla'

(*Aloë* 'Tiki Zilla')

Gasteria sp. × (*Gasteria* sp. ×
Aloë sp.) × *Aloë saponaria*

INVENTOR/PATENT

Paulus A. M. van der Meer,
Adrianus L. M. van der Meer
USPP25343P2, 13 Mar 2013

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Compact and upright plant habit; leaves arranged in a dense basal rosette; green-colored leaves with greyed green-colored margins and spots; upright flowering stems; good postproduction longevity.

×**Gasteraloë 'WT01'**

(*Aloë* 'WT01')

Aloë hybrid (*Aloë* × *Aristaloë*?) ×
Gasteria nitida

INVENTOR/PATENT

Wander Tuinier

USPP22012P3, 19 Oct 2009

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

'Strong, durable foliage, resistant to rot and breakage; fast, vigorous growth rate.'

Gasteria 'D Due'

Gasteria 'WT10'

INVENTOR/PATENT

Christian Jachertz

USPP29665P3, 12 Jan 2017

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Dark green glossy leaves with yellow-green dots; star-shaped rosette plant form.

***Gasteria* 'D Tiga'**

Gasteria 'WT10'

INVENTOR/PATENT

Wander D. Tuinier

USPP29488P2, 3 Mar 2017

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Upright rosette growth habit; dark green-colored leaves with numerous light green-colored tubercles; excellent interiorscape performance.

***Gasteria* 'Green Star'**

Gasteria 'WT03'

INVENTOR/PATENT

Wander D. Tuinier

USPP24763P2, 19 Dec 2012

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Upright habit; green leaves with light green spots.

***Gasteria* 'Royal Wolfgang'**

Gasteria 'WT10'

INVENTOR/PATENT

Wander D. Tuinier

USPP25667P2, 20 Sep 2013

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Dark green leaves with grey-green spots on the inner surface, white spots on the outer surface and margins with white teeth.

***Gasteria* 'WT10'**

Gasteria hybrid × *Gasteria* hybrid

INVENTOR/PATENT

Wander Tuinier

USPP23622P3, 21 Oct 2010

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Strong green foliage color with small grey-green dots; distinctive evenly whorled rosetting plant form.

***Gonialoë* 'Tiki Tahī'**

(*Aloë* 'Tiki Tahī')

Gonialoë variegata

INVENTOR/PATENT

Paulus A. M. van der Meer,
Adrianus L. M. van der Meer⁵
USPP23913P2 28 Nov 2011

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Compact and upright plant habit; leaves arranged in a dense basal rosette; green-colored leaves with white-colored spots and margins; upright flowering stems; good postproduction longevity.

***Haworthiopsis* 'African Albino'**

(*Haworthia* 'African Albino')

Haworthiopsis fasciata 'Big Band'

INVENTOR/PATENT

Antonius C. J. van der Hoorn
USPP24256P2, 24 Mar 2012

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Upright and outwardly spreading foliage with upright flower scapes; dark green-colored leaves with white-colored spots

⁵ No relation to the author.

on the upper surface and broad white-colored bands on the lower surface of the leaves; white and yellow green-colored flowers that are positioned above the foliar plane on moderately strong scapes.

Haworthiopsis
‘AMSTERDAM’

(*Haworthia* ‘AMSTERDAM’)
Haworthiopsis fasciata

INVENTOR/PATENT

Rogier Willems
USPP24415P3, 20 Jul 2012

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Small quantity of leaves; small white dots on leaves.

Haworthiopsis ‘L1’

(*Haworthia* ‘L1’)
Haworthiopsis limifolia

INVENTOR/PATENT

Peter Lock
US20110016594P1, 18 Jul 2009

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Unique white bands crossing the entire leaf surface; foliage occurs

in a single rosette, with no off-sets observed.

***Haworthiopsis* 'New York'**

(*Haworthia* 'New York')
Haworthiopsis fasciata

INVENTOR/PATENT

Rogier Willems
US20140026273P1, 20 Jul 2012

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Distinctive white spots pattern on foliage; Stronger roots; rapid growth rate.

***Tulista* 'SI HAW 7026'**

(*Haworthia* 'SI HAW 7026')
Tulista pumila × *Tulista pumila*
'Donut'

INVENTOR/PATENT

Wander D. Tuinier
USPP29693P2, 3 Mar 2017

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

Upright rosette growth habit; dark green-colored leaves with relatively large and orbicular white-colored tubercles; excellent interiorscape performance.

LITERATURE

United States Patent and Trademark Office (2019). 1601 Introduction: The Act, Scope, Type of Plants Covered [R-11.2013]. <<https://www.uspto.gov/web/offices/pac/mpep/s1601.html>>.

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